
ABSTRACT

Physical Education is an integral part of the total education process. A field of endeavour that has its aim in the development of physically, mentally, emotionally and socially fit citizens through the medium of physical activities that have been selected with a view to realize these outcomes. It is always a matter of concern in the society that those who play more are less interested in studies or the persons involved in sports are not good in academics. To find out the answers to certain queries in mind present research was done on the students of Engineering Colleges, Nagpur. The purpose of the present study was to find out the academic achievements of Sportsmen and non sportsmen and to compare the academic achievements of sportsmen and non sportsmen. To accomplish the purpose of the study academic data was collected from the college records. Total 346 student's academic scores were selected for analysis. 173 sportsmen participated in various games during the session were selected for the study and 173 non sportsmen data was randomly selected from the records. Sportsmen and non sportsmen were the enrolled students of Engineering colleges, studying in various branches viz. Electronic, Industrial, Civil, Mechanical, Electronics and Communications, Electronics Design & Technology, Electrical, Computer Science, Information Technology and MBA, MCA. The data collected was statistically analysed by using critical ratio, mean, S.D., t score. Percentage wise distribution of data was also done. On the basis of findings of this study it is concluded that there is difference in academic scores of sportsmen and non sportsmen. More Sportsmen were found in excellent category than Non Sportsmen. But when tested statistically for significant difference there is insignificant difference in the academic Scores of Sportsmen and Non Sportsmen.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern concept of physical education there is more emphasis on the noun education than the adjective 'physical' which precedes it. Physical education is not designed as education of the physical and education through the physical, here physical refers to body. In the programme of physical education activities are planned for all students who are considered normal, quiet a good number of students are not fit to participate with the majority of the students while the majority of the students participate joyously in the physical activities. Most schools /colleges offer some physical education When physical training has introduced into the curriculum, the teachers were little concerned about such an educational pattern physical training existed for exercise purpose only, for body development, for relief from the boredom of classroom drill. But to be educationally virtuous a programme must enhance - the growth of students in understandings, skills and attitudes. The curriculum of physical education should be arranged so that students have consecutive time to learn. Change in activity every day makes the curriculum a jerky disconnected experience given over more to amusement than to education. It is fundamental in good teaching to stay on something until you get somewhere with it. Academic achievements now a days is very necessary as it is needed for getting better job and to earn livelihood. It is always a matter of concern in the society that those who play more are less interested in studies or the persons involved in sports are not good in academics.

METHODOLOGY

The academic data was collected from the college records. Total 346 student's academic scores were selected for analysis. 173 sportsmen participated in various games during the session were selected for the study and 173 non sportsmen data was randomly selected from the records. Sportsmen and non sportsmen were the enrolled students of

Engineering colleges, studying in various branches viz. Electronic, Industrial, Civil, Mechanical, Electronics and Communications, Electronics Design & Technology, Electrical, Computer Science, Information Technology and including MBA and MCA.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data collected was statistically analysed by using critical ratio, mean, S.D., t score. Percentage wise distribution of data was also done. These tables were further statistically treated for calculating their critical ratios and significance was tested using the table values of 't'.

For finding out the significance in respect of academic achievement of students t score was applied.

Table -1 Table Showing percentage wise distribution of academic scores of sportsmen and non sportsmen

Grade Categories	Sportsmen %	Non sportsmen %
Outstanding	0.57	1.15
Excellent	16.18	8.09
Very Good	31.21	32.36
Good	28.90	31.79
Satisfactory	13.87	15.02
Average	2.89	3.46
Poor	6.35	8.09

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From the above shown table of percentage and graph it is clear that there is difference in excellent Category whereas very slight difference is seen in Very Good and Good category.

Hence there is slight difference in academic achievement of Sportsmen and Non Sportsmen in relation to their academic achievement.

Table -2 Table Showing the Significance of difference between Mean Academic scores of sportsmen and non sportsmen Students

Population	N	Mean	SD	df	t value
Sportsmen	173	7.35	1.44	172	1.28
Non Sportsmen	173	7.17	1.38		

Tabulated t= 1.97 at .05 level of significance.

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From table no 02 it is revealed that calculated t 1.28 is less than tabulated t which is 1.97 at .05 level of significance at degree of freedom 172.

Hence no significance difference is found in the academic achievement scores of sportsmen and non sportsmen.

FINDINGS

Percentage wise distribution of scores shows slight difference of 2% in academic scores of sportsmen and non sportsmen in some of the grade categories. 16.18% Sportsmen were found to be in Excellent Category whereas only 8.09% non sportsmen were lying in excellent category. Very good and Good Category shows very less difference in percentage. Sportsmen, non-sportsmen students did not differ significantly with respect to their academic Scores as 't' value 1.28 is less than the table value 1.97.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of findings of this study it is concluded that there is difference in academic scores of sportsmen and non sportsmen. More Sportsmen were found in excellent category than Non Sportsmen. But when tested statistically for significant difference there is insignificant difference in the academic Scores of Sportsmen and Non Sportsmen.

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